
BASUG LAW JOURNAL

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10501127>

CONSTITUTIONAL HISTORY ON LEGISLATIVE POWERS TO AMEND OR REPEAL: AMENDMENT OF TRADE TREATIES IN NIGERIA

*Sani Ibrahim Koki**

Abstract

The paper seeks to clarify the legislative competence to amend and or repeal any existing legislation. It also seeks to find from constitutional history whether the power of a country as sovereign state is capable of signing unilateral, bilateral, multi-lateral and optional treaties/agreements and as a dualist nation can ratify and domesticate these treaties /agreements for public peace and order whose efficacy is translated by courts through interpretations without legislative intervention. Some of these treaties/conventions are trade based directly or indirectly affecting Nigeria's foreign policy and the courts in themselves cannot in any way interpret these treaties and agreements. Further, World Trade Organization as global trade regulator has cardinal objectives- there is for instance, the principle of unfair trade incorporating trade remedies to check the excesses of erring members regarding violation of trade rules. Anti-dumping Agreement is a trade relief that calls for attention where there is injury or threat to either a product manufactured in the country or retards the establishment of an industry and it extends to the existing industries. This trade remedy has not been domesticated and the only relevant law to deal with this phenomenon is an obsolete Act of 1958. In 2010 Senator Patrick Enabule

sponsored a Bill to repeal the Act; the bill itself is inconsistent with the WTO ADA, thus unacceptable according to its objectives. Further, both the bill and the Act have not received any attention till today. And it is only the National Assembly that can ratify or domesticate international laws, conventions or agreements. The paper employed doctrinal, analytical and jurisprudential approach methodology and descriptive analysis using constitutional history, case laws, related literatures, journal articles, the Bill and certain WTO agreements. At the end the writer recommended that not only trade treaties need domestication and ratification, more importantly this obsolete Act of 1958 whose relevance cannot be over-emphasized. It also recommended that since trade treaties have direct bearing with economic policy, legislature should ensure the presence and participation of experts before signing any Trade Treaties, agreements and conventions.

Key Words: Trade Treaties, WTO, Anti-Dumping Agreement, Legislature, Nigeria.

1.0. INTRODUCTION

At the end of World War II caused by colonialism—empires crumbled and hopes blossomed everywhere. Third world leaders had hopes of their own, firmly believing that the key to development and material comfort depended on the attainment of political independence of the colonized territories¹. However, countries must associate with one another to survive as rightly observes by Adam Smith in 1776 and David Ricardo in 1817, hence, the need to form ad-hoc inter-relation for growth and development in the globe and this does not in any way temper with sovereign rights individual countries possess. This is achieved through treaties, agreements and conventions. There are also international institutions and multi-corporations that shape policies and laws within the domestic appear of all nations around the globe. World Trade Organization is a treaty-based global regulator of trade and possesses certain objectives for full participation amongst its members.

Treaty has been a fundamental principle at international level shaping how states deal with one another binding party which must be performed in good faith². In some countries, treaties or agreements must have been domesticated by a legislative instrument before it becomes enforceable within the municipal legal order³. This has been the position in Nigeria right from independence. Nigeria acceded to WTO agreement in 1995, hence the need to domesticate instruments forming the organization. There are General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT), Agreement on the Implementation of Article VI of the GATT (1947), known as Anti-Dumping Agreement both of which were replicated to form WTO in 1994. The Customs Duties (Dumped and Subsidized Goods) Act 1958 come as a result of Nigeria's participation in the GATT (1947).

*DCM, ADLS, LL. B(BUK), BL(Enugu) MBCL(BUK), LL.M(BUK), PGDE(FCEK), Principal Partner I.S. KOKI & CO. Legal and Corporate Consultants No. 1031, Ja'en Yamma (B) Sharada Phase III Gwale, Former Legal Officer and Part-Time Lecturer, FCE Kano, PhD (Bahri University Republic of Sudan, (in view)) Digital Bridge Institute and presently a lecturer with the Faculty of Law Yusuf Maitama Sule University, Kano. +2348032210192.sanikoki17@gmail.com.

¹ Ghana's first President, Kwame Nkrumah, preached a text for third world's new leaders: "Seek ye first the political kingdom, and all else will follow." also available at <<https://scholarlycommons.law.cwsl.edu/cwilj/vol27/iss2/4>, accessed on 26th April, 2023. See Christian N.Okeke, *International Law in the Nigerian Legal System*, CWSL Scholarly Commons, 1997.

² M.I. ANUSHIEM, *Implimentation of treaty as basis for regional cooperation Vis-à-vis Absolute Sovereignty: Nigeria in perspective*, NAUJILJ 8(1) 2017.

³ Ibid at pg 61.

Domesticating trade treaties or repealing obsolete laws in Nigeria is paramount because almost all sectors of the economy that are trade based have bearing in one way or the other with WTO commitment which Nigeria is signatory, the Act has not been amended since the first enactment nor repealed till date, while the Bill to repeal the Act has also not been attended to. The Anti-dumping agreement being a trade remedy brings relief to mostly manufacturing subsector for instance Cotton, Textile and Garment. This attitude leads to many of the local industries closing shops. In Kano alone before the coming of WTO there was at-least 19 Cotton, Textile and Garment Industries in operation but today none is optimally functional, some have been identified to operate on part-time basis⁴. In spite of these challenges the legislature plays disdainful attitude towards solving the problem. This is the relevance and why it is important to conduct this kind of study using doctrinal research methodology to articulate and analyze the legislative powers to amend or repeal any law that is obsolete and domesticate trade treaty which Nigeria is signatory especially the ADA and or to amend/repeal the related Act of 1958.

The paper discussed further the constitutional history on legislative powers and how treaties should be domesticated through the legislative process. The powers of the national assembly to amend or repeal laws that have been demonstrated to be simple and clear as provided by the constitution of the 1979 and 1999 respectively. One major aspect of the paper was the articulation of treaty categorization and analysis of the Patrick Enabuile's Bill to repeal the 1958 Act in line with WTO Anti-Dumping Agreement.

2.0 HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF NIGERIAN LEGISLATION

Historically, Nigeria ratified many treaties and conventions on environment, African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act⁵, Conventions on Biological Diversity 1992, Rio Declaration on Environment and Development 1992, Child Rights Act promulgated in 2003, the African Continental Free Trade Agreement signed by 54 African countries and brokered by the African Union(AU),establishing the African Continental Free Trade Area(AFCFTA) on March 21, 2018 amongst others. This agreement

⁴ Sani Ibrahim Koki, *"Examination of the Principle of Unfair Trade under WTO and Its Effects on Cotton, Textiles and Garment Subsector in Nigeria"* being an LLM Thesis submitted to Faculty of Law Bayero University, Kano. 2019.

⁵ Cap A9, LFN, 2004 (hereinafter called ACHPRA)

requires members to remove tariffs from 90% of the traded goods and services devoid of barriers. It is the largest free trade area aside WTO⁶ whose purpose was to create a unified continental trade agreement as a result of problems associated with the trade agreements between regional bodies in Africa⁷. African, Caribbean and Pacific agreement is another trade agreement; here there are structural changes and comparative disadvantage⁸ which also requires legislative intervention just like the ADA of the WTO. It appears however, that most trade based treaties have not received the attention of the legislature nor the Courts. The judicial attitude towards treaty implementation in Nigeria's constitutional history is not far-fetched from the *locus classicus* case of *Gen. Sani Abacha & 3 Ors. v. Chief Gani Fawehenmi* where the Supreme Court held:

*"An international treaty entered into by the Government of Nigeria does not become binding until enacted into law by the National Assembly. Before its enactment into law by the National Assembly, it has no such force of law to make its provisions justiciable in our Courts"*⁹.

3.0 CONSTITUTION AND TREATY MAKING

Today diplomats of any nation, whether they are negotiating trade agreements or participating in international conventions, must be ready to understand the outlook of others and know in what manner, and with what arguments, they hope to be persuasive. Such diplomats will not be successful in their diplomatic responsibilities if they are unable to appreciate the thinking of their foreign homologues,¹⁰ or if they speak and act as though they were dealing with persons from their own country. It is not surprising that in the international arena, representatives of different nations, with their very different intellectual processes and cultural backgrounds,¹¹ contemplate law and international relations in a manner very different from their counterparts in other countries.

⁶ Okey Oyama Ovat (et 'al) *African Journal of Business and Economic Research (AJBER) 2023, Vol 18, pg25.*

⁷ Woolfrey Sean Byiers Bruce, "The African Continental Free Trade Area and Politics of Industrialization" *ECDPM BLOG, Accessed on 20th July 2023.*

⁸ *Ibid* at pg25.

⁹ This was the tenor of section 12(1) of the 1979 Constitution now re-enacted in Section 12(1) 1999 Constitution.

¹⁰ See Christian N. Okeke, *op cit* note 1

¹¹ *Ibid.*

For example, in negotiations with the United States, Canada, England, or Nigeria, diplomats must know something about their respective constitutional law so that they can appreciate, in particular, the limitations under which their federal authorities really operate. International understanding can readily be enhanced and promoted between countries within regional schemes or communities of cooperation, as for example, in certain federal states or the various political and economic groupings established in Europe and on other continents, through the instrumentality of international law. And while international conventions and customary rules of international law promote a modicum of international understanding, the national courts of each country would facilitate such understanding by taking into account the way in which the problem put to them is resolved by the legislation or courts of other nations¹².

3.1 WHAT ARE TREATIES?

Treaties are direct agreements that are often in a form of auxiliary law undertaken by states.¹³ They are legal under both international and domestic law and bear a close similarity to contracts involving one, two or more parties to the agreement. A treaty is pact made by sovereign states which confer binding sets of obligation.¹⁴ It could be unilateral, multi-lateral and optional. It is an accord, consensus ratified, approved and endorsed by various countries/states in their local legislations.¹⁵ The word treaty and convention are used interchangeably but with slight difference in some cases and well defined by the Supreme Court in respect of its binding effect in Nigeria¹⁶.

Treaty and convention can only acquire legal efficacy where a process is duly followed at the legislative instance. For treaty to be effective no matter how prudent must be ratified and domesticated.¹⁷ In Nigeria a treaty would not have binding effect unless such treaty is enacted into law.¹⁸

¹² Ibid.

¹³ Yinka Olomajobi, Jessica Oga, *Nigeria: Between Monist and Dualist State*; International Journal of Legal Developments and Allied Issues, Vol. 8 issue 4.

¹⁴ Article 2(1)(a) of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaty, 1969.

¹⁵ Yinka op cit note 13.

¹⁶ *Abacha v Fawehinmi* [2000] 6 NWLR 228.

¹⁷ *Higgs & Anor v Minister of National Security & Ors* {2000} 2WLR 1368.

¹⁸ See Section 12(1, 2 and 3) of CFRN 1999 (as amended)

3.2 TREATIES IN NIGERIA.

The discussion about treaty in Nigeria started from colonial period and had been the genesis of its rooted problems when King Dosumo was forced to sign treaty of protection, the content of which he did not understand nor had any knowledge. But even under the European Law at that time such treaties were invalid because they were obtained through intimidation.¹⁹ Treaty law should be clear on who enters into it, and the conditions for its efficacy, then binding authority to its formation. Nigeria has a foreign policy objectives clearly defined that are either clearly expressed or implied²⁰ and started upon attainment of political independence and later captured under the 1963, 1979 and 1999 constitutions²¹ respectively.

In Nigeria treaty making begins from the Executive arm which initiate the process through the Ministry of Foreign Affairs while the National Assembly plays crucial role in foreign policy making²² which possesses the decisive position of approving and disapproving treaty/agreement entered, power to suggest changes in the text for Executive to negotiate afterwards.²³ The 1963 constitution at its preamble only provided a system for implementation of treaty without conferring power on the parliament²⁴. The 1979 only implied treaty promotion and dealt with any law that is inconsistent with its provisions²⁵ while the 1999 respects the doctrine of Dualism in the application of treaty...meaning treaties or agreements are not self-enforcing unless acted upon by the National Assembly²⁶. This is a transformation vested on the legislature being Nigeria a dualist state

¹⁹ Umozurike argues that the Vienna Convention did not "create but merely re-affirmed these principles for they were in existence when the treaties were concluded with African Kings." Umozurike O. Umozurike, *International Law and Colonialism in Africa*, 3 E.A.L. Rev. 47 (1970). Mutua gives a succinct description of the unacceptable nature and character of the treaty signed by King Dosumo: The absolutist language of the "treaty", its one-sided capitulation by Dosumo, and the complete, unconscionable "renunciation" over the sovereignty of his people, territory, and resources is of such absurdity that, if taken seriously, it would make a mockery of the notion of a treaty and the concept of freedom of contract. Makau wa Mutua, *Why Redraw the Map of Africa: A Moral and Legal Inquiry*, 16 MICH. J. INT'L L. 6 (1995).

²⁰ See Section 19 of CFRN 1999 (as amended)

²¹ See Section 12(1 and 3) CFRN 1979.

²² Dunmoye, R.A., Njoku, P. and Alubo, O. (2007). *The National Assembly: Pillar of Democracy*(Ed.) Abuja: *The National Secretariat of Nigerian Legislatures, National Assembly*.

²³ Ibid at pg. 121.

²⁴ Section 74 of the 1963 Constitution.

²⁵ See Sections 12(1)(2)(3) of the 1979 Constitution FRN

²⁶ Section 12(1)(2)(3) of the CFRN respectively.

as reiterated in 'Registered Trustee of National Association of Community Health Practitioners of Nigeria & Ors. v Medical and Health Workers Union of Nigeria'²⁷.

3.3 TRADE TREATY CATEGORIZATION

Economists tell two stories about the function of trade treaties/agreements: postulating that they restrain protectionism, or else restraining the purposeful exploitation of market power²⁸. While protectionism and terms-of-trade manipulation are distinct though often confused, trade agreements might restrain both²⁹. It is however argued that trade agreements especially the Preferential Trade Agreements (PTAs) provide strong institutional incentives to prevent international conflict among member states, often creating the conditions of trust that can help prevent militarized aggression³⁰. It is further argued that despite Nigeria's participation in many trade agreements that has not really led to its economic growth and development,³¹ this is basically the reason behind the paper. Generally, treaties or agreements are categorized based on their relevance to suit the purpose for which they are intended. The most common, or perhaps well-known, agreements are Bilateral Investment Treaties and Free Trade Agreements and not all trade agreements are Free Trade Agreements³².

Treaties/Agreements may take the form of Unilateral, Bilateral and Multi-Lateral. Anti-dumping Agreement is multi-lateral agreement forming WTO's institutional frameworks. Unilateral trade agreements are trade incentives which an importing country offers in order to encourage the exporting country to engage in international economic activities that will improve the exporting country's economy³³ mostly to developing countries. Bilateral and Multi-lateral agreements are reciprocal treaties where the benefits are reaped by exporters and importers depending on the category below;

²⁷ AA Oba, 'The African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights and ouster clauses under the military regimes in Nigeria: Before and after September 11' (2004) 4 (2) *African Human Rights Law Journal*.

²⁸ Donald H. Regan (2006) *Journal of International Economic Law Vol 9(4) Oxford Academic*.

²⁹ *Ibid* at pg. 1.

³⁰ Emile M. Hafner-Burton, Alexander H Montgomery, (2012) War, Trade, and Distrust: Why trade agreements don't always keep the peace. Sage Journals. Also at sagepub.com accessed on 20th July, 2023.

³¹ Fidelis C UWAKWE, Theophilus Nwoke, (2023) *A critical Review of the Impediments to International Trade Agreement and Development in Nigeria*. Unizik Law Journal 15.

³² [Http://www.springer.com/978-3-642-19807-6](http://www.springer.com/978-3-642-19807-6), *Origin Management, Rules of Origin in Free Trade Agreements*, van de Heetkamp, A; Tusveld, R, 2011, XVIII, 237 p., Hardcover. (accessed on 22nd July, 2023)

³³ *Ibid* pg. 35.

- a. First Category; treaties here must constitute rules governing inter-state relationship and cooperation with effect of altering or modifying existing legislation. ADA is a good example in this regard.
- b. Second Category; these are agreements which impose financial, political and social obligations in Nigeria and are scientific or technological importing, for instance ILO³⁴.
- c. Third Category; this category refers to treaties dealing with mutual exchange of cultural and educational facilities³⁵.

4.0. LEGISLATIVE COMPETENCE TO AMEND OR REPEAL TREATY

The most distinguishing feature in today's constitutional engineering is separation of powers notably referred to as the Doctrine amongst the different organs or branches of government³⁶. This doctrine guides for proper organization of powers and governmental units, department, directorates within the confederating units like states and local governments. It is the most effective embodiment of spirit underlying the government itself³⁷. The concept is founded on the existential fear that when power is concentrated in one person or group of persons like on only legislative arm the tendency to abuse same is obvious³⁸.

Right from independence, successive governments in Nigeria have engineered different constitutions all providing for this doctrine with the latest found in the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria³⁹. The doctrine of separation of powers articulates government distinction, independence and ensuring that no organ exercises the powers of another⁴⁰. It has also been described to mean that one branch should not control or

³⁴ Fidelis op cit note 31.

³⁵ See Peter Obi at pg 155.

³⁶ O.B. Adebite; O.O. Oduniyi; J.A. Farinde; *Seperation of Power under the 1999 Nigeria Constitution, the Core Legal Dilemmas* 2019 Sriwijaya Law Review, vol 3 Issue 2, July 2019. Pg 235.

³⁷ M.J.C. Vile, *Constitutionalism and the Separation of Powers*, (Indianapolis: Liberty Funds inc; 2nd edn 1998). Pg1-443.

³⁸ O.B Adegbite; O.O. Oduniyi Y A Farinde Op cit pg 23.

³⁹ This Constitution is more notoriously referred to as Decree No. 24 of 1999, as the last act of Military Law making by the administration of General Abdussalami Abubakar .

⁴⁰ A. Hamilton; J. Madison; and J. Jay, *The Federalist*: A. Collection of Essays, Written in favour of the New Constitution as Agreed upon by the federation Convention September 17, 1787 (The Law Book Exchange ltd) pg. 1-628.

interfere with the work of another, thus the legislative, executive and judicial powers are distinct.

Nigeria's constitution makes frantic effort to intelligently allocate powers and functions amongst the three branches of government and their various subsidiaries⁴¹ to ensure efficiency in governance, delivery and prevent the exercise of arbitrary power⁴². The constitution has been carefully departmentalized such that governmental powers are in three branches namely- Legislative under section 4, the Executive under section 5 and the judiciary under section 6 in the manner that separates the arms and all with distinct powers⁴³.

These provisions i.e. Sections 4,5 and 6 of the 1999 Constitution provide powers for the Legislature to make laws for the order and good governance of Nigeria as re-affirmed in the leading Supreme Court's decisions in Attorney General of Bendel State V Attorney General of the Federation⁴⁴. The Supreme Court this time per Eso Justice of Supreme Court (J.S.C) speaking on the doctrine said:

Now it's time that the Legislature, especially in a country like ours which has accepted the doctrine of separation of powers and which has got that doctrine embodied in constitution, is a master of its own household⁴⁵.

Additionally, the Court opined in Unongo V. Aper Aku that:

The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1979 which is hereafter referred to as the Constitution is very unique compared with the previous constitutions in the executive, the legislative and the judiciary are each established as a separate organ of Government.

The founder of this Fine face's view advocates for the guarantee of human liberty in which each sphere should be independent and supreme⁴⁶. The Nigerian Constitution made

⁴¹ A Phillips. "Nigeria's Federal Financial Experience; (1971), 9 (3) The Journal of Modern African Studies, pg. 389-408 also at O.B Adegbiti, O.O Odunniyi J.A Farinde, Op at pg 240.

⁴² *Keyamo V. House of Assembly of Lagos (2000) 12 Nigerian Weekly Law Report, part 218.*

⁴³ O.B Adegbite O.O Adeniyi J.A Farinde; Op cit note 30 pg. 236

⁴⁴ (1981)10 Supreme Court no.1 at pg. 198.

⁴⁵ (1982) 2 NCLR 509.

⁴⁶ (1983)2 SC NLR 332at 361

provisions for each arm of government to survive independently⁴⁷. In a democratic system, lawmaking is thought to be tedious and long process but seemed to be opposite in reality because of the adoption of the doctrine of separation of powers.

4.1. NATIONAL ASSEMBLY;

The power of the National Assembly to make laws shall be exercised by bills passed by both Senate and House⁴⁸. There is collective exercise between Federal legislature on appropriation bill or any other bill for the payment, issue or withdrawal from Consolidated Revenue Fund⁴⁹. The National Assembly also has power to regulate its own procedure, including the procedure for summoning and recess of the house⁵⁰. Vacancy, presence or participation of any person not entitled to be present at or to participate in the proceedings of the House shall not invalidate those proceedings⁵¹. These and many more powers presupposes the independence of Legislature to deal with any treaty/agreement entered by the Executive Arm through the process of bill making.

4.2. POWERS TO AMEND OR REPEAL LAWS

The general powers of national Assembly to make, amend or repeal laws are encapsulated under section 4 of the constitution as stated inter alia consisting Senate and House of Representatives. These laws shall be for the whole or any part of the Exclusive Legislative List set out in Part 1 of the Second Schedule to the Constitution of Nigeria 1999⁵². These powers are extended in respect of any matter in the Concurrent Legislative List as set out in the first column of part II of the Second Schedule to the Constitution or any other matter as the constitution provides⁵³. And in the event of conflict where State Law is inconsistent with the law of National Assembly the latter law prevails⁵⁴. Although the treaty-making power rests on Executive the power of domesticating same rests on legislative shoulder.⁵⁵

⁴⁷ I.C.Godsweath, Z B. Ahmad, J.A. Jawan, *Factors influencing the Executive and Legislative Conflict in Nigeria Political Development*. 105R Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, Vol 21 issue 8 (August, 2016) pg. 20.

⁴⁸ Section 59CFRN

⁴⁹ Section 60CFRN

⁵⁰ Section 61CFRN

⁵¹ Section 62CFRN

⁵² Section 4(1) CFRN.

⁵³ Section 4 (2).

⁵⁴ Section 4(2) (a)(b) See the Concurrent List under the first Column of Part II of the Second Schedule.

⁵⁵ Section 4 CFRN.

4.2.1. THE PURPOSE TO LEGISLATE

The general purpose of National Assembly laws or Legislations is captured well in that to make laws for the peace, order and government of the Federation with respect to matter included in the Exclusive Legislative List⁵⁶, this is clear manifestation that laws are meant to safeguard public peace and order which result in giving assurances to economic prosperity.

4.2.2. INTENDMENT

Laws made by the National Assembly are intended to give or confer jurisdiction on courts of law and judicial tribunals. This allows courts to interpret these laws for peace, order and good government of the Federation or any part thereof⁵⁷ in some jurisdictions most trade treaties are interpreted by courts to suit domestic purposes. In Nigeria there are conflicting positions regarding treaty/agreements on superiority between municipal and statutes with international flavour as per Ogundere JSC in *Abacha v. Fawehenmi* where the apex court rules that except for the Constitution, treaties are of higher status than municipal laws⁵⁸.

5.0 ANALYZING THE ANTI-DUMPING AND COUNTERVAILING BILL, 2010 FOR LEGISLATIVE GUIDE;

The proposed Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, was sponsored by Senator Patrick Enabuile in 2010 and replicated by Hon. Abdullahi Umar Farouk in 2015 respectively and has been lying down at the National Assembly till date comprising 75 sections, divided into thirteen parts. For the purposes of this paper it is divided into substantive and procedural provisions.

5.1. SUBSTANTIVE PROVISIONS

Part I, section 3 provides for the definitions and interpretations of various terms and concepts used in the Bill. In more practical terms, “definitions” serve the purpose of clarifying concepts and attaching a specific meaning to a word or phrase as intended by the

⁵⁶ Section (4) (5).

⁵⁷ Section 4(3) See the Executive Legislative List under the Second to the 1999 Constitution.

⁵⁸ Section 254(C)(2). CFRN as amended.

draftsman. In other words, they define and confine concepts to a particular meaning.⁵⁹ The Bill seeks, partly, to provide for anti-dumping and countervailing measures in the country's trade transactions but does not define "anti-dumping measures" or "antidumping duty" in the list of interpretations.

Notably, it attempts a definition of "countervailing measures"⁶⁰ another trade remedy and provides a definition for "countervailing duty" as "a special duty to be levied for the purpose of offsetting subsidy granted directly or indirectly on the investigated product". This omission creates a fundamental gap in the Bill as to what "measure," or whether a "duty" would be imposed under Nigeria's anti-dumping legislation in the event of a determination of dumping.

The ADA provides for the application of "anti-dumping measures" and the circumstances of their application⁶¹. Under the ADA anti-dumping measures can take the form of either anti-dumping duties or price undertakings⁶². The ADA also provides that provisional payments may be applied before anti-dumping duties.⁶³ In other words, "anti-dumping measures" refers to provisional measures, anti-dumping duties and price undertakings, and "all measures taken against dumping" as stated by the Appellate Body in the case of US - 1916 Act⁶⁴. The absence of a clear definition, in the Bill, of these fundamental concepts is not only inconsistent with the spirit of the ADA but creates challenges of implementation from the onset.

5.1.1. DUMPING

The ADA provides that "a product is to be considered dumped, i.e. introduced into the commerce of another country at less than its normal value, if the export price of the product exported from one country to another is less than the comparable price, in the ordinary course of trade, for the like product when destined for consumption in the

⁵⁹ K Clark & M Connolly „A guide to reading, interpreting and applying statutes" (2006) The Writing Centre, George Town University Law Center www.georgetown.edu/.../legal.../statutoryinterpretation.pdf (accessed 17 March 2022-07-28).

⁶⁰ Part I sec 3 Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

⁶¹ Part I Art 1 Anti-Dumping Agreement.

⁶² Arts 8 & 9 Anti-Dumping Agreement.

⁶³ Art 7 Anti-Dumping Agreement.

⁶⁴ WTO Analytical Index: Anti-dumping Agreement.

exporting country”⁶⁵. This definition reveals four important concepts: normal value, export price, ordinary course of trade and like product. The Bill defines “dumping” as “the situation where the export price of goods imported or intended to be imported into Nigeria is less than the normal value of such goods in the market (country) of origin as determined in accordance with the provisions of this Act.

The Bill appears to have introduced an additional concept not envisaged by the ADA in its definition. In terms of the Bill, “export price of goods imported” as well as those “intended to be imported” will be considered in the determination of “dumping”. This “new definition” creates a challenge as to how to determine the normal value, export price, and “likeness” of a product “intended to be imported” into Nigeria, in the ordinary course of trade. This definition is problematic and at variance with the object and purport of the ADA.

5.1.2. EXPORT PRICE

The export price is a fundamental consideration in the determination of dumping. In terms of the ADA, the export price is the price at which the product is exported from one country to another⁶⁶. However, the export price may also be constructed in certain circumstances⁶⁷. Unlike the definition of export price in the ADA, the Bill defines export price as – “a price paid or payable for an export destined to the Country⁶⁸”. This definition is problematic in two respects. First, the reference to “the Country” in that definition is most confusing and leaves one to conjecture as to which country is the destination of the exported product.

Second, the definition is limiting to the extent that, it does not apply to products sold for export, but only those actually exported⁶⁹. For instance, an invoiced export price is normally either Free on Board (fob) or Carriage Insurance and Freight (CIF) price. The price actually paid for the goods sold (export price) should be net of all taxes, discounts and

⁶⁵ Part I sec 3 Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

⁶⁶ Art 2.1 Anti-Dumping Agreement.

⁶⁷ Art 2.3 Anti-Dumping Agreement; see para 2.7.2 on „constructed export price. “

⁶⁸ Part I sec 3 Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010 (n 2 above).

⁶⁹ This information was gained from an interview with Dr. Gustav Brink, International Trade Law Consultant and Associate Director at XA International Trade Advisors, Centurion, South Africa (20 January 2014).

rebates granted and related to the sale of the goods in consideration⁷⁰. Although the Bill, seem to provide details as to considerations to be made in the calculation of export price,⁷¹ these cannot be regarded as “a cure” for the defect. The need to create an effective antidumping framework consistent with the provisions of the ADA calls for an amendment of the current definition of “export price” as contained in the proposed Bill.

5.1.3. INTERESTED PARTIES

In an anti-dumping proceeding, the foreign exporters, their importers and the domestic producers of the product being investigated are three key interested parties. They all are directly affected by the investigation as the outcome would significantly influence future investments⁷².

The Bill defines “interested parties” to include – “(b) the government of the origin of the investigated product; (c) a producer of the like product in the territory or a trade or business association with a majority of the members who produce the like product in the territory⁷³.” This definition needlessly imports circumstances not contemplated by the ADA. Whilst the paragraph (a) of the definition in the Bill seem to align word for word with the ADA, the preceding paragraphs (b) and (c) cited above fall short of the clear provisions of the ADA in this regard. Rather than adopting the simplicity of the term “exporting Member” as used in the ADA, the Bill uses the expression “the government of the origin of the investigated product”.

Not only is this expression subject to more than one interpretation because the origin of the investigated product may be different from the exporting member, it does not explicitly recognize the exporting country government as intended by the ADA thereby establishing a basis for difficulty in interpretation and implementation. In the paragraph following, the word “territory” referred to is unspecified and there is no certainty as to the meaning of the word “territory” as used in the paragraph. These definitions as set out in the Bill, creates circumstances and standards that are clearly not in line with the spirit of the ADA⁷⁴.

⁷⁰ GF Brink ‘Anti-dumping and countervailing investigations in South Africa: A practitioner’s guide to the practice and procedures of the board on tariffs and trade’ (2004) 63.

⁷¹ Part III sec 17 Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

⁷²Op cit Vermulst.

⁷³ Part I sec 3 Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

⁷⁴ Art 6.11(i) (ii) & (iii) Anti-Dumping Agreement; See ch 2 para 2.5.4 on „Interested parties. “

5.1.4. RELATED PARTIES

The ADA provides a comprehensive interpretation of the term “related parties”⁷⁵. Within the context of the ADA, determination of the “domestic industry” is significantly connected with the definition of “related parties”. In an anti-dumping proceeding, not all parties are interested parties and a proper definition of the term guarantees the exclusion of “unrelated parties” as intended by the ADA. As observed by Brink, the definition of the concept of “related parties” may impact the determination of normal value and export price⁷⁶. Interestingly, the Bill provides an interpretation of “domestic industry”⁷⁷ but fails to define the term – “related parties”. These definitional gaps fall short of consistency with the WTO standards as set out in the ADA and would pose a challenge to effective implementation of the anti-dumping rules.

5.1.5. NORMAL VALUE

The concept of “normal value” and the different ways of normal value determination were well captured in the ADA⁷⁸. The concept of “normal value” is defined in the Bill as “the price comparable to the export price, in the ordinary course of trade, for the investigated product when destined for consumption in the investigated country”⁷⁹.

This definition clearly and erroneously disregards the reference made in the ADA definition to “the like product” and “the exporting country”⁸⁰. It may be seen that the Bill, provides further details as to the determination of “normal value” and severally made references to “country of export”⁸¹. Upon a closer look, the Bill in the determination of “normal value” fails to provide for “nonmarket economies”⁸². Paragraph (a) – (c) provides exceptions to the application of section 11 where the investigated products – “are not produced in the country of export; are merely trans-shipped through the country of export from the country of origin or; have no comparable price for such products in the country of export.

⁷⁵ Art 4.1 Anti-Dumping Agreement; See para 2.5.5 on „related parties. “

⁷⁶ GF Brink ‘A theoretical framework for South African anti-dumping law’ unpublished PhD thesis, University of Pretoria, 2004 761.

⁷⁷ Part I sec 3 Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

⁷⁸ See Article on ADA normal value.

⁷⁹ Part I sec 3 Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

⁸⁰ Art 2.1 Anti-Dumping Agreement.

⁸¹ Art 11 Anti-Dumping Agreement.

⁸² See para on „non-market economy normal value. “

The Bill is silent as to what would be the rule in these exceptional circumstances. This oversight creates a fundamental deficiency in the proposed national anti-dumping legislation considering the fact that China is one of Nigeria's major trading partners and has been treated by other trading partners, in some circumstances, as a non-market economy⁸³. The reliance of the drafters of the Bill on ambiguous words and terms where the ADA is clear and precise has not achieved the intended objective of aligning Nigeria's anti-dumping rules with its WTO obligations.

6.0. ANALYZING THE ANTI-DUMPING AND COUNTERVAILING BILL, 2010: PROCEDURAL PROVISIONS FOR LEGISLATIVE GUIDE

6.1. INITIATION AND INVESTIGATION,

This part discussed the concept and procedural guidelines of "initiation" under the WTO ADA⁸⁴. With reference to the panel ruling in Thailand-H-Beams, the ADA provides clearly defined obligations that must be met before the initiation of an investigation. Consequently, a WTO member seeking a remedy against a violation of an Article 5 obligation has a duty to specify which paragraph of Article 5 is violated and at the very least identify the specific sub-paragraphs of that Article that is being alleged to have been violated⁸⁵.

Upon receiving an application, the investigating authority, has to take the further step of determining the sufficiency of evidence to justify the initiation of an investigation. The investigating authority is required to – first, examine the accuracy and adequacy of the evidence contained in the application and; second, determine whether the applicants are sufficiently representative of the domestic industry, in other words, whether the applicants have the "standing" required to bring the case⁸⁶.

The proposed Bill sets out the procedure for initiation of investigation in providing as follows – "upon receipt of application by or on behalf of an industry, the Minister assisted

⁸³ K Oporum "Nigeria is third largest trade partner of China: Chinese envoy" All Africa 10 July 2013.<http://allafrica.com/stories/201307100758.html> (accessed 22 March 2022); Vermulst pg45; Brink 180-181.

⁸⁴ See the bill on initiation and subsequent investigation.

⁸⁵ Panel Report, Thailand – anti-dumping duties on angles, shapes and sections of iron or non-alloy steel and h-beams from Poland (2000) World Trade Organization WT/DS122/R para 7.23 [http://www.worldtradelaw.net/reports/wtopanels/thailand-steel\(panel\).pdf](http://www.worldtradelaw.net/reports/wtopanels/thailand-steel(panel).pdf) (accessed 23 March 2022); Vermulst Op cit pg 102.

⁸⁶ Arts 4.1, 5.3 & 5.4 Anti-Dumping Agreement.

by the department responsible for trade shall examine the accuracy and adequacy of the evidence provided in the application to determine whether there is sufficient evidence to justify initiation of investigation⁸⁷". It further provides – "where the Minister is satisfied that, sufficient evidence exists in favor of an investigation, he shall convene the Committee for that purpose".

In view of the provisions cited above, the proposed Bill imposes two obligations for the initiation of an investigation⁸⁸: examination of the accuracy and adequacy of the evidence provided in the application to determine whether there is sufficient evidence to justify initiation of investigation and; the discretionary decision of the Minister as to sufficiency of evidence in favour of an investigation. The latter requirement of the Bill appears to have substituted the ADA "standing" requirement for the Minister's discretionary decision.

6.2. COMMITTEE MEETING

Furthermore, the Bill provides for "initiation of investigation by the Committee⁸⁹". The Bill also provides for the "meeting of the Committee"⁹⁰ in response to the "special circumstances" contemplated by section 28. However, the Bill fails and or neglects to provide for "normal procedures"⁹¹ that is, the ordinary applications requiring more frequent meetings which section 8 cannot be said to have provided for. The procedures proposed by the Bill for the initiation of investigation seems suspicious, lacking in transparency, constitutes a potential threat to implementation of the law on anti-dumping and not in compliance with the ADA requirements.

6.3. RETROACTIVE IMPOSITION OF ANTI-DUMPING DUTY

The Bill makes provision for the imposition and collection of anti-dumping duties⁹². It also specifically provides for the imposition of anti-dumping duties on a "retrospective" basis⁹³. However, the Bill does not contain provisions specifying the reasons or circumstances under which an anti-dumping duty would be applied retrospectively. In terms of the ADA,

⁸⁷ Part V sec 27(3) Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010

⁸⁸ Ibid Part V, Sec 27(3).

⁸⁹ Part V sec 28 Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

⁹⁰ Part II sec 8(2) Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

⁹¹ Part V sec 28 Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

⁹² Part IX sec 57(2) Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

⁹³ Part IX sec 52(2) Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

anti-dumping duties may be imposed retroactively to a date 90 days prior to the imposition of provisional measures, under the following critical circumstances:

1. There is a history of dumping which caused injury or that the importer was, or should have been, aware that the exporter practices dumping and that such dumping would cause injury, and;
2. The injury is caused by massive dumped imports of a product in a relatively short time which in light of the timing and the volume of the dumped imports and other circumstances (such as a rapid build-up of inventories of the imported product) is likely to seriously undermine the remedial effect of the definitive anti-dumping duty to be applied, provided that the importers concerned have been given an opportunity to comment”⁹⁴.

6.4. REFUND APPLICATIONS

The ADA provides elaborate guidelines regarding “refund applications”⁹⁵. The Bill provides: “where the amount of the anti-dumping or countervailing duty is assessed on a prospective basis, provision shall be made for a prompt refund, upon request to the government of any duty paid in excess of the margin of dumping or subsidization”⁹⁶. It further provides: “a refund under subsection (4) shall be made within twelve months, and in any case not exceeding eighteen months after the date on which a request for a refund, duly supported by evidence, has been made by an importer of the product subject to the antidumping or countervailing duty and such refund shall be made within ninety days from the day the decision was made”.

Notably, the Bill neither indicates to whom the application for refund must be made nor who must refund it. This is in direct contravention of the ADA requirements that provision “...shall be made for a prompt refund, upon a request, of any duty paid in excess of the margin of dumping.

6.5. OFFENCES RELATING TO INFORMATION

The last section of the Bill deals with “offences relating to information”⁹⁷. In terms of the section of the Bill, where a person willfully gives false or misleading information to the

⁹⁴ Art 10.6(i)(ii) Anti-Dumping Agreement.

⁹⁵ See the proposed bill on refund applications.

⁹⁶ Part IX sec 57(4) Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010).

⁹⁷ Part XIII sec 75 Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

Committee or discloses a confidential information provided in the course of an investigation without the permission of the Committee and without „lawful excuse⁹⁸” refuses to provide the Committee with an information requested, contravenes the Act and commits an offence punishable upon conviction by a fine not exceeding two million naira ⁹⁹ (N2,000,000) or imprisonment for a term not exceeding six months or to both.

Although, the ADA continues to function as a framework agreement and leaving substantial discretion to Member countries in the application of the rules, it does not in its entirety, either by way of express provision or inference, provide for “penalizing” or “criminalizing” an exporter for non or incomplete co-operation or refusal to provide information¹⁰⁰. The ADA envisages a situation in which one or more interested parties may decide not to cooperate in an investigation. In the event that an interested party does not supply the required information within a reasonable time, or refuses authorities access to its relevant information or significantly hinders the investigation, the ADA allows for preliminary and final determinations to be made on the facts available. This provision of the Bill which seeks to penalize and criminalize an exporter for none or incomplete co-operation is outrageous and at variance with the spirit, object and purport of the WTO ADA.

6.6. ADVISORY COMMITTEE

It is important that any system set up for the purpose of balancing the interests of local industries against those of their foreign counterparts be seen to be fair, objective and transparent in its composition and operations. The Bill seeks to establish an Advisory Committee¹⁰¹ (Committee) to carry out certain functions contemplated in the Bill¹⁰². The Committee consist of: (a) the Chairman; (b) one member representing the Federal Ministry of Commerce; (c) one member representing the Federal Ministry of Finance; (d) a representative of the Attorney-General of the Federation; (e) one member representing the Nigeria Chambers of Commerce, Industry and Agriculture; (f) one member representing the Federal Ministry of Industry; (g) one member representing the Federal

⁹⁸ The term “lawful excuse” or what would amount to an „unlawful excuse is not defined in the Bill.

⁹⁹ The “naira” is Nigeria’s currency.

¹⁰⁰ See Sec 36 of the proposed bill.

¹⁰¹ Part II sec 6 Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

¹⁰² Part II sec 5(a - i) Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

Inland Revenue Service; (h) one member representing the Standard organization of Nigeria; (i) one member representing the National Planning Commission; and (j) one member representing the National Agency for Food Administration and Control (NAFDAC)¹⁰³.

Section 6 provides a list of functions of the Committee as follows:

- (a) Advising the Minister generally, on the proper implementation of the provisions of the Act;*
- (b) Advising on urgent measures necessary for the protection of domestic industries from injury caused by dumping or subsidy;*
- (c) Ascertain whether the investigated product, through the effect of dumping or subsidization, cause or threatens material injury to industry or producer;*
- (d) Advise the Minister on policy issues related to this Act;*
- (e) Perform any other duties related to this Act assigned to it by the Minister;*
- (f) Recommend to the Minister the imposition of antidumping or countervailing measures appropriate action; and*
- (g) To conduct investigation on such matters as the Minister may determine¹⁰⁴.*

The inclusion of a representative from the Nigeria Chambers of Commerce, Industry and Agriculture (the Chambers) appears to indicate that the Committee may be expected to be biased in favor of the local industry in the conduct of anti-dumping investigations, its advisory function to the Minister, its recommendations to the Minister as to the appropriate measures to be imposed, and this may well be the major reason why a separate department or institution should be saddled with the responsibility for anti-dumping investigations to the exclusion of the Chambers. In point of fact, the Chambers represents the interests of local companies and businesses in Nigeria with the primary objective of “promoting, supporting or opposing legislative or other measures affecting trade,

¹⁰³ Part II sec 5(a - i) Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

¹⁰⁴ Part II sec 6(a - g) Anti-Dumping and Countervailing Bill, 2010.

industry, commerce and agriculture as well as representing the opinion of the business community on the above matters in particular, and the economy as a whole¹⁰⁵.

7.0. CONCLUSIONS

The need for Legislative arm to wake up for the emancipation of Nigeria's foreign trade policy is eminent especially at World Trade Organization. Nigeria accented to this agreement but without legal regime concerning dumping. Dumping has been so problematic to the extent that members domesticated the Anti-Dumping Agreement in their respective countries taking anti-dumping measure against any exporting member that violates the ADA, but Nigeria becomes dumping ground for almost everything including Garri made from cassava. Nigerians are price sensitive so they pick almost everything at rock-bottom price and substandard goods, it is only when the legislature intervenes then the treaties signed and domesticated or amend and repeal the obsolete Customs Duties (Dumped and Subsidized Goods) Act of 1958 would be usable for development, economic prosperity peace, order and good government of Nigeria as an independent Nation.

Considering the historical milestones in the Nigeria's constitution making on the legislative power to amend or repeal laws has been well captured in our respective constitutions. This powers included in the 1999 Constitution which allows the legislature to domesticate any treaty/agreement/convention that is signed and acceded by Nigeria and for the benefit of Nigerians which will ultimately give respect for the country at global level. The 1999 Constitution spelt out procedure upon which laws are made, amended or repealed and on whose head these powers are conferred. There are many treaties mostly in relation to trade whose content needs to be ratified and domesticated for their immense benefit to the Nigerian populace especially where there are visible effects as in trade sector where liberalization has always been at the fore-front leaving the stakeholders at the mercy of foreign competitors. The Customs Duties (Dumped and Subsidized Goods) Act 1958 came 10 years or so after the enactment of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade 1947 and the Act was meant to address issues raised in that agreement and not ADA of WTO that

¹⁰⁵ About the Chamber <http://www.lagoschamber.com/profile-of-the-lcci/> (accessed 7 April 2022).

came lately in 1995 and this has direct economic consequences which may lead to unemployment.

8.0. RECOMMENDATIONS

The signed treaties/agreements should be domesticated through legislation by the Legislature taking into account their relevance to economic growth, development and nation's prosperity. As these unsigned agreements would have direct economic consequences on the economic sovereignty of Nigeria and governmental policy at international level especially now that Nigeria is over dependent on almost everything.

It is also recommended that National Assembly should as a matter of urgency revisit the previous bill sponsored by Senator Patrick Enabule from Edo State and Hon. Abdullahi Umar Farouk from Katsina State for legislative action and to ensure its conformity with WTO and ADA to be assented by the President, this call is clarion.

Nigeria's legislature should prioritize trade agreements any time the Executive arm intends to participate in its making so that domestication of such treaty/agreement would come at ease where experts' opinions are first sought and advice obtained. This illuminates the role and efficacy of treaty/agreements to the citizenry and policy formulation in the country.